

5th European Workshop on Maritime Systems Resilience and Security (MARESEC 2025)

21 – 22 May 2025 // Rostock, Germany

PROCEEDINGS

Editors

Peter Danielis

Helge Parzyjegl

Stefan Lüdtke

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Peter **Danielis**, *University of Rostock, Germany*

Helge **Parzyjgla**, *University of Rostock, Germany*

Stefan **Lüdtke**, *University of Rostock, Germany*

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The **5th European Workshop on Maritime Systems Resilience and Security (MARESEC 2025)** took place on 21–22 May 2025 in Rostock, Germany.

Message from the Chairs

The *European Workshop on Maritime Systems Resilience and Security* (MARESEC) is committed to advancing the exchange of the latest research results, technological developments, and innovative concepts among stakeholders from academia, research institutions, industry, and public authorities. The workshop serves as a forum for presenting and discussing approaches to strengthen the resilience, safety, and security of maritime systems, addressing both technological advances and societal dimensions. Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, cybersecurity, autonomous systems, digital twins, underwater technologies, and the ethical, legal, and social aspects of maritime innovation.

The fifth edition of MARESEC took place on 21–22 May 2025 in Rostock, Germany, hosted by the University of Rostock as a hybrid event. In total, 102 participants joined the workshop: 86 on-site and 16 remotely. The program featured 32 presentations, of which 26 delivered in person and 6 online. Participants represented universities, research institutions, industry, and other sectors, with strong representation from Germany, other European countries, and further abroad.

The Technical Program Committee put together a diverse and high-quality program comprising 10 technical sessions, two keynote addresses from leading experts in academia and industry, and an industry panel on maritime autonomy. The contributions reflected the breadth and multidisciplinary character of research in maritime systems resilience and security, covering a wide range of technological, operational, and societal perspectives.

We extend our sincere thanks to all authors for their valuable contributions, to the reviewers for their thorough and constructive evaluations, and to the keynote speakers and panelists for sharing their expertise and insights. We also gratefully acknowledge the commitment of the local organizing team and the valuable support of our partners — the Digital Innovation Centre and Rostock Business — as well as the generous sponsorship of EvoLogics as the exclusive sponsor of MARESEC 2025.

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, it is our pleasure to present the proceedings of MARESEC 2025. We hope that the work collected here will contribute to advancing research, strengthening collaboration, and fostering innovation in the vital field of maritime systems resilience and security.

Peter Danielis, General Chair

Helge Parzyjgla, Program Chair

Stefan Lüdtke, Publication Chair

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Keynotes

Maritime Security

Fabian Bannasch, *EvoLogics, Berlin, Germany*

Abstract. Although approximately 70% of the Earth's surface is covered by oceans, the exploration and sustainable development of the marine environment are still in their early stages. EvoLogics, a company specializing in advanced underwater communication and positioning technologies, contributes to this effort through ongoing technological innovation. In his keynote, Fabian Bannasch will present EvoLogics' award-winning bionic submersible robots that are inspired by the form and movement of penguins and manta rays. Designed for diverse operating environments, these systems support a wide range of applications: from measuring salinity and temperature in the ocean over assessing water quality in rivers to identifying ecologically sensitive zones to be preserved during deep-sea mining activities. In addition, the robots can assist in inspecting underwater infrastructure such as pipelines and the foundations of offshore wind turbines. Fabian will illustrate how these robotic systems are part of a larger, networked underwater ecosystem. Combined with the innovative use of artificial intelligence, they enable new maritime applications that improve the maintenance and protection of critical infrastructure.

Fabian Bannasch holds a Bachelor's degree in Business Economics from Humboldt University in Berlin and an MBA from the European School of Management and Technology (ESMT), also in Berlin. He began his career as an R&D engineer and assistant manager at EvoLogics before joining McKinsey & Company in 2009. There, he held various consulting roles and eventually became a senior expert in product development. His work focused on product strategy, technology roadmaps, product excellence, and R&D process optimization across industries including automotive, mechanical engineering, industrial goods, and consumer electronics. In 2020, Fabian returned to EvoLogics as Managing Director and owner, leading the company in its second generation. Since then, EvoLogics has expanded with new divisions in Robotics, Sensor Systems, and Artificial Intelligence, while continuing to advance underwater communication and positioning technologies. Outside the office, Fabian is often found around the water—both below and above the

surface—as a certified rescue diver, a licensed pilot, and currently as a trainer of a water rescue dog.

Engineering Resilience Before the Storm Hits

Sascha Kosleck, *Ocean Engineering, University of Rostock, Germany*

Abstract. For decades, this phrase could be taken quite literally in the field of ocean engineering. Preparing systems to withstand the physical forces of nature has long been at the core of maritime design. But today, resilience must go far beyond structural integrity. As maritime systems become increasingly complex, automated, and interconnected, engineers and operators face a new wave of challenges. Cybersecurity threats, dual-use concerns, and evolving safety demands are reshaping what it means to build and maintain trust in maritime environments. This keynote explores how our understanding of resilience must evolve to meet these multidimensional risks—before the next storm hits, in every sense of the word.

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Sascha Kosleck has held the Chair of Ocean Engineering at the University of Rostock since July 2019. Prior to this, he led the Maritime Engineering Department at Auckland University of Technology in New Zealand for six years. His academic career began with a degree in Civil Engineering from the Technical University of Berlin in 2004, followed by his doctorate in 2013 with the dissertation titled "Prediction of Wave-Structure Interaction by Advanced Wave Field Forecast." For this work, he was awarded the Curt Bartsch Prize by the German Society for Maritime Technology. Prof. Kosleck's research focuses on the hydrodynamics of offshore structures, the development of deterministic wave forecasting, and the optimization of systems for offshore oil spill recovery. He is also involved in the development of underwater technologies with a focus on pressure-tolerant systems for deep-sea operations. As Head of the

Department of Maritime Systems at the Interdisciplinary Faculty of the University of Rostock and Co-Spokesperson of the Ocean Technology Campus Rostock, he is committed to interdisciplinary collaboration and to training the next generation of engineers in the sustainable use of marine resources.

Industry Panel

A highlight of MARESEC 2025 was the industry panel, which brought together leading voices from innovation, consulting, and analytics to explore both the opportunities and challenges of developing scalable, cooperative autonomy in the maritime domain.

Panelists

Fedor Ester, *Demcon Unmanned Systems*

Georgios Grigoropoulos, *Kpler*

Frithjof Mess, *EvoLogics*

Ralf-Martin Tauer, *CGI Deutschland*

Moderation

Helge Parzyjegla, *University of Rostock*

The photo above shows (from left to right) Frithjof Mess (EvoLogics), Georgios Grigoropoulos (Kpler), Ralf-Martin Tauer (CGI), and Helge Parzyjegl (University of Rostock), who participated on-site. Fedor Ester (Demcon Unmanned Systems) joined remotely via video call (top of the image). The lively exchange covered technological, operational, and regulatory perspectives ranging from prototyping and testing to real-world deployment at scale. The discussion centered around the two main topics.

Topic #1: Towards Collaborative Maritime Autonomy – Scaling from Single Vessels to Maritime Fleets

While single autonomous vessels are increasingly operational and valuable, real transformation may come through cooperation: fleets of autonomous ships, collaborative port operations, and seamless interaction between manned and unmanned systems. This part of the discussion explored what is required to move from stand-alone autonomy to multi-agent coordination in the maritime domain.

Topic #2: Bridging the Gap – Maritime Collaboration Between Industry, Research, and Technology

The panel also explored how to foster stronger collaboration between the maritime industry, research institutions, and technology developers. Discussion focused on how partnerships can be made effective, what conditions are needed for success, and the mutual benefits they bring, such as faster innovation, practical solutions, and sustainable long-term impact.

The industry panel provided participants with valuable insights into both the state of the art and the path ahead. We thank the panelists for sharing their expertise and perspectives.

Helge Parzyjegla, Program Chair

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Colin **von Negenborn**, *University of Hamburg, Germany*

Michael **Wagner**, *Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf; Technical University Dresden, Germany*

Chathura **Wanigasekara**, *German Aerospace Centre (DLR), Germany*

Carl **Wrede**, *German Aerospace Centre (DLR), Germany*

Technical Program

Wednesday, May 21		Thursday, May 22	
08:00	Registration	Registration	08:00
08:30	Welcome to MARESEC 2025	Introduction to Day 2	08:30
	Keynote #1 Fabian Bannasch	Keynote #2 Sascha Kosleck	
09:20	Session on Navigation and Localization	Session on Communication and Security	09:20
10:40	Coffee Break	Coffee Break	10:40
11:10	Session on Dependability Modeling	Session on Vessel Tracking and Route Planning	11:10
12:30	Lunch	Lunch	12:30
13:30	Industry Panel	Session on Maritime Autonomy	13:30
14:30	Coffee Break	Session on Maritime Imaging	14:30
15:00	Session on Threat Assessment	Coffee Break	15:30
16:00	Session on Legal and Social Aspects of Future Vessels	Session on Artificial Intelligence	16:00
17:00		Session on Advanced Sensing Technology	16:40
		Farewell MARESEC 2025	17:50
18:30	Boarding		
	Gala Dinner & River Cruise		
22:00			

Session on Navigation and Localization

ORMOBASS - Increasing resilience of navigation in the Baltic Sea

Lars Grundhöfer, Stefan Gewies and Filippo Giacomo Rizzi

Navigating Polar Routes: An Open-Source Simulation Framework for Autonomous Shipping structured on SLAM

Klára Orbán, Stefan Lüdtke and Kuderna Iulian Bența

Trade-Off Between USBL Update Rate and Pose Estimation Accuracy in Factor-Based SLAM

Maximilian Popko, Sebastian Bader, Stefan Lüdtke, Philipp Bannasch and Thomas Kirste

Numerical Studies of Object Localisation Using Ocean Acoustic Tomography

Michaela Murzyniec and Ireneusz Czajka

Session on Dependability Modeling

Resilience assessment in a container terminal with fuzzy logic

Stefanie Gote, Jan Stockbrügger and Frank Sill Torres

Maritime cocaine trafficking through containers from South America to Europe: an agent-based model

Maykol Rodriguez Prieto

An Agent-based Model to Analyse Threat Scenarios for Offshore Windparks

Lara Beßmann and Frank Sill Torres

Maintenance schedule optimization for offshore wind farm by configuration of operational windows and job sorting

Georges Anicet Kuete Kouam, Bartosz Skobiej, Arto Niemi, Nikolai Kulev, Andrzej Jardzioch and Frank Sill Torres

Session on Threat Assessment

Navigating diffuse maritime information settings: A heuristic for improved analysis of hybrid threats

Lukas Albrecht and Tjorven Harmsen

Digital Defense at Sea: Cybersecurity Toolbox for Autonomous Maritime Systems

Ravishankar Borgaonkar and Dikshant Devkota

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Maritime World Model for Data-Based Threat Assessment

Jannik Klemm, Jan Stockbrügger and Frank Sill Torres

Session on Legal and Social Aspects of Future Vessels

Autonomous Ships and the Application of Flag State Law to Land-Based Operation Centers

Jason Halog

The Legal Qualification of Modular Crafts as Ships

Paul Margat

From Emergence to Acceptance: Towards a Technology Acceptance Model for a Next Generation Underwater Mothership

Alena Schmitz

Session on Communication and Security

On Cryptographic Issues in Maritime Logistics

Daniel Berger and Aaron Lye

Remote control of ship systems via rogue devices: exploiting insecure fieldbus communication

Marvin Davieds, Richard Dabels and Thomas Mundt

CargoAssist: Hybrid Communication Approach for Cargo Monitoring and Anomaly Detection

Mohamad Omran, Tim Brockmann, Frank Golatowski and Christian Haubelt

Liebherr Future-Proof Offshore Maintenance: Crane Operations and Security Strategies in Focus

Julia Hrdinka and Patrick Jussel

Session on Vessel Tracking and Route Planning

A Minimalist Approach to Store AIS Data Using PostgreSQL-PostGIS and Rust

Jose Luis Quinones Gonzalez, Tino Flenker, Yannik Steiniger, Jannik Klemm and Arto Niemi

Onboard Radar Processing Framework for Maritime Surveillance with a High-Altitude Platform

Sushil Kumar Joshi and Stefan V. Baumgartner

Real-Time Vessel Collision Forecasting and Avoidance Using Distributed Computing

Georgios Grigoropoulos, Ilias Chamatidis, Marios Vodas and Konstantina Bereta

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Two phase path planning for fuel-efficient safe navigation

Hiba Ben Lahbib, Aqsa Yaseen, Abdullah Mughees, Shehroz Khan, Gaadha Sudheerbabu, Juri Vain, Mohamed Taha Bennani and Dragos Truscan

Session on Maritime Autonomy

Energy Consumption Optimization of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles Using Power State Machines

Ghazal Hodaei, Peter Danielis, Willi Brekenfelder, Helge Parzyjegla and Frank Sill Torres

Cooperative Mission Planning for Autonomous Vehicles

Paul Stube, Helge Parzyjegla, Willi Brekenfelder, Frank Sill Torres, Peter Danielis and Frank Golasowski

Framework for Heterogeneous Multi-Domain Swarms to Improve Maritime Situational Awareness

Stefan Kampmann, Sarah Barnes and Maurice Stephan

Session on Maritime Imaging

Pipe Reconstruction from Point Cloud Data

Antje Alex and Jannis Stoppe

Acoustic 3D reconstruction of underwater infrastructure – possibilities, problems & potentials

David Brandt and Benjamin Lehmann

Comparison of different image processing techniques for VIS-NIR images in maritime environments at night

Tristan Preis, Laura Kontschak, Alexander Klein, Jendrik Schmidt, Maurice Stephan and Enno Peters

Session on Artificial Intelligence

REGMAR (MarineTime Regulation): LLM-Based RAG & Multi-Agent AI for Maritime Cybersecurity

Yonghun No, Haerin Lee and Yonghyun Jo

Leveraging Large Language Models for Information Extraction of Subsea Data Cable News

Jonas Franken, Kasimir Romer, Timon Dörnfeld, Paula Meissner and Christian Reuter

Session on Advanced Sensing Technology

Development of a Submersible Membrane Inlet Photoionization Mass Spectrometer (MI-PIMS) for the Detection of Aromatic Compounds in Sea Water

Carolin Schwarz, Thomas Kröger-Badge, Fabian Etscheidt, Christian Gehm, Sven Ehlert, Dorothée Niethammer, Johannes Passig, Thorsten Streibel and Ralf Zimmermann

Cherenkov detector with wavelength-shifting fiber readout for muon tomography applications

Anzori Heorhadze

A modular and flexible hodoscope for industrial muon imaging

André Bieberle, Uwe Hampel, Guruprasad Rao, Suzanne Eisendorfer and Michael Wagner

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